

MESO-SCALE MULTIPHYSIC MODELLING OF THE WET FILAMENT WINDING PROCESS

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Abstract

The ability to control process variables and knowing their influence in final properties of laminates are major intents in any composites manufacturing process. In this research program, the wet filament winding process was studied and modelled in detail. The several physical phenomena interacting at the layer/laminate level were described independently and a meso-scale overall decoupled original model was established. Upon this architecture, a numerical code was devised and implemented. Finally, a comprehensive experimental program was conducted to measure and evaluate all the process variables. Partial and full validations of the process model were, thus, progressively achieved. The constitutive relations developed, together with the experimental results supporting and/or validating them are presented and discussed throughout this paper.

1 Introduction

In the FW manufacturing process there are several physical parameters whose different combinations allow a wide range of mechanical and geometrical results. These parameters may be divided into two categories: the user controllable process parameters and the other process parameters inherent to the physics of the process. In a process model development, the final objective is to get the user controllable process parameters to be the input variables and the inherent variables (which are not directly controllable throughout the process) to be the output ones. Only with sound and correct physical descriptions of each phenomenon one may get a profitable tool for design and process optimization purposes.

The main user controllable process parameters are:

- the choice of the materials (fibres and matrix);
- the geometry of the mandrel;
- the initial fibre's tension;

- the cross section of the fibre's bundle (incl. bandwidth and/or thickness);
- the path of the fibres onto the mandrel;
- the winding angle;
- the initial degree of fibre's impregnation;
- the processing temperature;
- the winding speed;
- the lay-up sequence; and
- the curing schedule and cycle after winding.

On the other hand, the main process inherent phenomena, which vary with time and space without direct control from user, are:

- the fibre's motion within laminate;
- the matrix flow through the fibre's bed;
- the degree of conversion of the matrix (cure/crystallization);
- the matrix viscosity;
- the stresses and strains in the fibres;
- the material temperature;
- the local fibre's, resin's and void's volume fractions; and
- the fibre's characteristic and/or local waviness.

A few more parameters could be pointed out, such as the permeability of the fibre bed to the resin and air, or the layer's interaction by way of the compaction pressure and resin mixing. However, these may be identified as sub-parameters that influence the respective parents, previously identified. Moreover, these sub-parameters need to be specifically analysed in each case as they highly depend on the material system used together with other main options for the FW process configuration.

One- and two-dimensional resin flow/fibre compaction process models have been developed in the last three decades [1]. Most of the studies were not specifically dedicated to the FW process. Nevertheless, their assumptions, modelling strategies and specific features are of great interest in gathering the sense and knowledge to develop this multi-physical process model, since many of the

interacting phenomena are common to several of these manufacturing processes.

A few studies were, nevertheless, dedicated to FW. Springer *et al.* [2,3] presented a process model for FW of thin and thick composite cylinders with thermosetting resin systems. Gutowski *et al.* [4,5] developed laminate consolidation models and then applied it to the FW process case [6]. Spencer [7] established an analytical model to predict the resin cure state, layer's locations and residual stress state in orthotropic filament-wound composite cylinders. Based on early descriptions of Springer *et al.* [3], Olofsson [8,9] and Ikonopoulou and Marchetti [10] coded partial process models for FW.

Despite the numerous studies conducted on composites processing through the years, and the specific ones on FW, there is still lack of consensual and fully validated models for the FW process. The process models developed so far, haven't been fully validated and/or have a limited range of applicability. In fact, due to the complexity of implementing a testing apparatus in a typically cylindrical FW laminate, most of the experimental data used to validate FW process models was gathered out of the real process setup.

In the present study, analytical descriptions of the different physical phenomena acting in the FW process were established and are presented in the following sections. The identification of the phenomena governing the consolidation process at the layer/laminate level was achieved by combining the knowledge gathered through a comprehensive literature review, the study of the physics of the process and the practical experience on the process. In addition, several unique experimental procedures were designed and implemented in order to assess either input or output quantities, thus validating the modelling strategy quite comprehensively.

2 Multiphysic Process Model

Herewith, the several sub-process physical phenomena are analytically described through either original or previously developed relations. Each group of phenomena corresponds to a sub-model within the multiphysic global model.

2.1 Thermo-chemical Behaviour of the Matrix

The thermo-chemical curing behaviour of thermosetting polymer matrices (resins) is a major aspect in the overall consolidation of the laminates being manufactured. The degree of cure, α , and the

viscosity, μ , drive, respectively, the extent of crosslinks occurred up to each moment and the ability of the resin to flow through the porous fibre bed. The former was characterized by combined isothermal and dynamic differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) while the latter was assessed through viscosimetry and rheometry tests.

The selected resin was the commercial epoxy SR[®]1500 which presents formulation bases of bisphenol A and F. The resin system used was a mixture of the resin with the amine hardener SD[®]2505 in the ratio of 100:33% by weight, respectively.

In order to simulate the "real" conditions to which these resins are subjected during the manufacturing, curing and post-curing of composite laminates, manufacturer's recommended cure cycles (MRCC) were imposed. The MRCC for the SR[®]1500 resin consisted in single isothermal dwells at near-to-room temperatures. This approach was rarely used by previous authors.

The detailed descriptions of the test procedures, samples preparation and analysis of results were published elsewhere [11,12].

Fitting the data curves, two original phenomenological models were established for the selected commercial epoxy/amine system (SR[®]1500/SD[®]2505 from Sicomin, France) for the range of processing temperatures. These models are called hereafter Karkanis Extended and Extended Lee. They were adapted from the Karkanis kinetic [13] and Lee rheological [14] models and are described, respectively, as

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{C(\alpha - \alpha_{\max})}} [k_1 (1 - \alpha)^{n_1} + k_2 \alpha^m (1 - \alpha)^{n_2}] \quad (1)$$

and

$$\mu = \mu_{\infty} e^{\frac{U}{RT^a} + k_1 (\alpha - b \alpha_{gel})} \quad (2)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are rate constants and m , n_1 and n_2 are reaction order constants, α_{\max} is the maximum degree of cure achieved in each applicable isothermal cycle, C is a constant, μ_{∞} , U , R , a and b are constants, α_{gel} is the degree of cure at which gelation occurs and T is the resin temperature.

These models presented good agreement with the experimental data obtained for the different

temperatures tested, as can be observed in Figs.1 and 2, respectively.

Fig.1. Fitting of Karkanas extended model to the experimental DSC isothermal data of SR@1500/SD@2505 at 30°C (303K), 40°C (313K) and 50°C (323K).

Fig.2 - Fitting of Lee and Extended Lee models to the experimental rheometry data of SR@1500/SD@2505 samples tested at 30°C (303K), 40°C (313K) and 50°C (323K).

2.2 Consolidation Pressure

The kinematics of the filament winding process is largely substantiated in the transfer of a winding force, $F_{winding}$, imposed to the fibre tows into a radial pressure, p , which develops throughout the thickness of the laminate. Its gradient induces a subsequent outward resin flow. From the analogy with thin cylinders subjected to internal pressure a relationship between those process variables was firstly found for the case of hoop winding. It took the form:

$$p = \frac{t^l \sigma_{\theta\theta}}{r} = \frac{F_{winding}}{r_{initial} b}, \quad (3)$$

where p is the pressure, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$ is the hoop stress, r is the reference radius of the wound layer, $r_{initial}$ is the reference radius of the wound layer at initial state, t^l is the thickness of the wound layer, $F_{winding}$ is the

winding force imposed to the fibre bundle and b is the fibre bundle bandwidth. As a new layer is wound, additional external pressure is applied to the fibre bed beneath composed by the previously wound layers, thus creating a pressure gradient in the laminate. The radial pressure at the inner surface of the generic j th layer, p^j , is the sum of the pressures acting in the layers that lie on it, which is represented by:

$$p_{winding}^j = \sum_{i=j}^n \frac{F_{winding}}{r^i b^i}, \quad (4)$$

where n is the number of wound layers, r^i is the reference radius of the i th layer ($j < i \leq n$), b^i is the fibre bundle bandwidth of the i th layer.

Due to the inward motion of the fibres the circumferential stresses, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, may be partially released and so the radial pressure. An integrative relation was developed to account for both the initial winding kinematics (winding angle, ϕ) and the remaining mechanical behaviour during winding and consolidation:

$$p = \left[\frac{F_{winding} \sin \phi}{r_{initial} b} + \frac{t^l}{r} \frac{(E^f V_f^j + E^m V_m^j)(r - r_{initial})}{r_{initial}} \right] \sin \phi, \quad (5)$$

where E and V are the elastic-apparent moduli and the relative volume content. The super- and sub-scripts f and m refer to fibre and matrix, respectively. Combining equations (4) and (5), the following comprehensive relation was settled for the pressure at the j th layer:

$$p^j = \left[\sum_{i=j}^n \frac{F_{winding} \sin^2 \phi^i}{r_{initial}^i b^i} \right] + \frac{t^l}{r^j} \frac{(E^f V_f^j + E^m V_m^j)(r^j - r_{initial}^j)}{r_{initial}^j} \sin \phi^j, \quad (6)$$

2.3 Resin Flow and Media Permeability

As a new layer is wound the ones beneath are further compacted (radial pressure gradient develops) and the resin is squeezed outwards. The saturated fibre bed permeability, S , and the resin viscosity, μ , govern the flow through adjacent layers. The transverse permeability of the saturated fibre bed is given by [15]:

$$S = \frac{r^{f^2} \left(\frac{\sqrt{V'_a}}{\sqrt{V'_f}} - 1 \right)^3}{4k' \frac{V'_a}{V'_f} + 1}, \quad (7)$$

and the resin flow radial velocity, \dot{u} , is then calculated using the Darcy's type equation [16]

$$\dot{u} = -\frac{S}{\mu} \frac{dp}{dr} \quad (8)$$

In order to compare with the analytical and numerical calculations, an experimental technique was developed to assess the two parameters. Certain layers were colorized to differ from the neighbour ones. The measurement of the colour gradients allowed to determine the outward radial distance flown by the resin. An example of the cross-section of a filament wound specimen is shown in Fig.3.

Fig.3. Cross-sectional views of the inner (left), mid (middle) and outer (right) regions of the wound specimen's thickness with one colorized layer.

2.4 Resin Mixing

The mixture of resins of adjacent layers may alter significantly the kinetic and rheological behaviour. This is a particular feature of the filament winding process. Such phenomenon is enhanced whenever the winding times are longer or the resins have different curing histories prior to their mixture. A linear combination formulation was adopted upon previous studies [17] to describe the contribution of the "strange" portions of resin to a certain layer to its effective viscosity.

$$\mu = \sum_{j=1}^m \Psi_j^m \mu_j \quad (9)$$

However, results from dedicated experiments conducted in the viscosimetry and rheometry apparatuses have shown that this relationship is only applicable for the very early stages of the mixture. In reality the newly mixed resin portion will progress with a different (uncharacterized) rheological behaviour [18]. Nevertheless, the linear combination approach provides a reasonable approximation.

2.5 Fibre Bed Compaction

As a newly wound layer "crosses" the resin rich layer (typically formed in the outer perimeter of the laminate) it compacts the layers beneath. It progressively compacts itself. Therefore, the quantity of resin contained in the layers tends to decrease during the process. The laminate's consolidation is then characterized by an increase of the relative content of fibres, V_f . A direct relationship was devised as

$$\frac{dv_T}{dt} = \frac{dv_r}{dt} = A_{RVE} \frac{d}{dt} (r_o - r_i) \quad (10)$$

Experimental assessment to the radial positions, r , of each layer allowed to compare with the model results, showing very consistent and agreeing values. Input and output fibre contents were also measured through burn-off tests to further validate the model predictions.

2.6 Fibre Waviness

Fibre waviness is another intrinsic characteristic of the filament winding process. Typical values of $L/a \geq 100$ were firstly reported by Cai and Gutowski [5] for typical processing materials and conditions. However, in the winding experiments carried out in this research program, averaged values of $L/a = 20$ were consistently observed and were further used.

2.7 Stress-Strain

The stress-strain constitutive relations were firstly addressed in previous publications [19,20]. The main assumptions and simplifications driving the development of the constitutive relations were:

- the fibre bundles have an orthotropic behaviour, instead of a transversely isotropic one. The radial compaction that occurs during the process, leads to different elastic properties in the local 2- and 3-directions;
- The reference unit cell considered is a portion of the wavy fibre bundle, as depicted in Fig.4.

Fig.4. Reference unit (waved) cell.

- the homogenized properties of the lamina are retrieved from the constituents' weighed properties;
- the local on-axis (1,2,3) stiffness components are assessed from transforming the regular orthotropic stiffness matrix and then averaging its components over one wavelength;
- the resin flow and thus the fibre bed compaction phenomena occur only in the radial direction, r , across the laminate's thickness;
- due to the storage conditions, bundle twisting and other process-related events, the fibres are assumed to have a waviness pattern characterized by a function of the type [5]:

$$z = \frac{a}{2} \left(1 - \cos \frac{2\pi x}{L} \right) \quad (11)$$

where z is the transversal position measured perpendicularly to the "ideal" axis, x , along the fibre, a and L are, respectively, the characteristic amplitude and length of the sinusoidal pattern of the fibres.

- Resin intrinsic properties that depend on the degree of cure, such as thermal expansion coefficient, β , chemical shrinkage coefficient, η , and thermal conductivity, k , are assumed to vary linearly between the known initial and final values. Also the "elastic-apparent" constants of the resin, like Young's modulus, E^m , shear modulus, G_{ij} and Poisson's ratios, ν_{ij} , are assumed to vary in the same manner with the degree of cure, α . The following piecewise linear relations are considered to represent the variation of such properties before and after the resin reach gelation, α_{gel} :

$$\begin{cases} Y = \bar{\alpha} Y^c + (1 - \bar{\alpha}) Y^{uc} & \alpha < \alpha_{gel} \\ Y = Y^c & \alpha \geq \alpha_{gel} \end{cases}, \quad (12)$$

where Y represents any of the above mentioned material properties, Y^{uc} and Y^c its known values at the initial reference cure state and after cure (consolidation), respectively. The quantity $\bar{\alpha}$ is the ratio defined as:

$$\bar{\alpha} = \frac{\alpha - \alpha_0}{\alpha_{gel} - \alpha_0}. \quad (13)$$

From the various methods available to determine the composite homogenized properties [21-25], the Mori-Tanaka method was selected and used.

Within the frame of the present process model, the stress-strain constitutive relations are used to calculate the stress components given the strain and stiffness tensors at each instant. The total strain components account for the thermal expansions, $\beta\Delta T$, and chemical shrinkage, $\eta\Delta\alpha$, effects, and are given by:

$$\{\varepsilon_T\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} - \beta_{11}\Delta T - \eta_{11}\Delta\alpha \\ \varepsilon_{22} - \beta_{22}\Delta T - \eta_{22}\Delta\alpha \\ \varepsilon_{33} - \beta_{33}\Delta T - \eta_{33}\Delta\alpha \\ \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{31} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

The classical local on-axis constitutive orthotropic stiffness matrix, $[C_{ij}]$, defined as [26-28]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{13} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C_{13} & C_{23} & C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{55} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (15)$$

is populated with the updated layer elastic-apparent constants calculated from Mori-Tanaka method [25], and the averaged transformed ("waved") local stiffness matrix, $[\bar{C}_{ij}^{wav}]$, which accounts for the fibre waviness, is calculated as follows [29]:

$$[\bar{C}_{ij}^{wav}] = \frac{1}{L} \int_0^L [T^{wav}]^{-1} [C_{ij}] [R] [T^{wav}] [R]^{-1} dx, \quad (16)$$

where $[T^{wav}]$ is the waviness transformation matrix for each θ at each point, $[R]$ is the Reuter matrix, x is the fibre “ideal” axis and L is the wavelength of the sinusoidal pattern of fibres.

The constitutive relationship at the local on-axis coordinate system, keeping the consideration of orthotropic material, is thus given by:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \tau_{23} \\ \tau_{31} \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = [\bar{C}_{ij}^{wav}] \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} - \beta_{11}\Delta T - \eta_{11}\Delta\alpha \\ \varepsilon_{22} - \beta_{22}\Delta T - \eta_{22}\Delta\alpha \\ \varepsilon_{33} - \beta_{33}\Delta T - \eta_{33}\Delta\alpha \\ \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{31} \\ \gamma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (17)$$

3 Model Validation

A numerical code was written based on the multi-physical descriptions of each group of phenomena. A modular code was thus devised, allowing to parametrically test the behaviour of the main process parameters. A preliminary set of tests were conducted to simulate real experimental winding conditions (which were conducted as well). The main results are presented in Figs 5 to 7 for two pre-selected winding cases. A good agreement between numerical predictions and effective experimental measurements made in-situ was observed for early stages of the winding and consolidation process. Minor disagreements were observed, however, and their causes identified. These refer to inadequate stop criteria for resin flow and maximum applicable permeability. Improvements are now being addressed in the model in order to set the first fully functional and validated FW process model.

3 Conclusions

the multi physical model developed in this study has shown consistent and coherent results when compared with reliable and dedicated experimental data. The degree of validation for the winding conditions pre-selected is reasonably high, thus suggesting a correct approach and methodology. The model was capable of wisely relate the input with the output relevant parameters of this process, thus allowing to foresee reliable design and controls of the FW manufacturing process for each application. The modular structure and the comprehensive

experimental validation carried out further enhance the potential utility of the model developed upon advised improvements.

Fig. 5 - Evolutions of the pressure (numerical simultaneous/sequential and experimental) for two winding cases tested for the inner-most, middle, next to outer-most and outer-most layers.

Fig. 6 - Evolutions of the layer's thickness (numerical simultaneous/sequential and experimental) for two winding cases tested for the inner-most, middle, next to outer-most and outer-most layers.

Fig. 7 - Evolutions of the fibre volume fraction (numerical simultaneous/sequential and experimental) for two winding cases tested for the inner-most, middle, next to outer-most and outer-most layers.

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